

Secondary Schools' Support and the Performance of Student-Athletes in Sports Competitions: Basis for a Training Plan

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Abstract:- This study aimed to determine the relationship between the extent of schools' support in sports training and the performance of student-athletes in sports competition as an input for a Sports Training Plan for the Cluster I Secondary School in the Division of San Pablo City. It specifically answered how do the respondents perceived the schools' support in terms of Academic Support, Sports Equipment and Facilities, Financial Incentives, Health and Well-being, and Capacitating trainers/coaches. Moreover, it determined the level of student-athletes' performance in sports competitions held in the Cluster Meet, Division Meet, Regional Meet and National Meet. Also, it explored the relationship between the school support and performance of student athletes. The study was descriptive with a researcher-made questionnaire as the instrument of the study. The questionnaire was administered to 166 student-athletes of the schools under the Secondary Cluster I District who have participated in any sports event during the school year 2018-2019. The data collected were treated frequency count, percentage, mean scores, standard deviation, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Result revealed that the respondents assessed schools' support to be to a moderate extent in terms of academic support, sports equipment and facilities, financial incentives, health and well-being, and capacitating trainers/coaches. Further, analysis showed no significant correlation between the perceived extent of schools' support in sports training and the student athletes' performance in sports competition at 0.05 level of confidence.

Keywords:- Sports Training, Schools' Support, Student Athletes, Sports Performance

I. INTRODUCTION

Sports is a major contributor to economic and social development. Sports and physical education provide a boundless opportunity for learners to head outside, be active and dynamic, and concentrates on developing different skills. The benefits of sports in education are vast, and they aren't just physical benefits. Fundamentally, physical education and sports can have a wide array of health-related benefits to anyone.

The World Health Organization (WHO) Sports and Health Program was established to capitalize on the great potential of helping people worldwide lead healthy lives through promoting participation in sports and working with the sports community to advance health for all. The overall objective of the WHO Sports and Health Program is to accelerate progress on Sustainable Development Goal 3, which is to ensure healthy lives and promote wellbeing for all at all ages. In line with this, the World Health Organization (2015) discussed the following activities: (1) raising awareness - stimulate sports environments to promote the health and well-being of visitors, fans, players, employees, and communities, globally, nationally and locally ; (2) mainstreaming health - promotion of health and its benefits through physical activity and educational health promotion programs ; (3) keeping sports safe - assist in making sports safe by preventing injuries, social exclusion and violence and ; (4) making sports as a platform for health - increase health legacy for major sports event, increase national capacity of counties where major sports events take place in relation to prevention of diseases outbreaks, food/water/air safety, health promotion, and safety and health security at mass gatherings

In addition, role of sports is well recognized by the government, including in the Political Declaration of the 2030 Agenda, which reflects on "the contribution that sports make to the empowerment of women and of young people, individuals and communities, as well as to health, education and social inclusion objectives.

In the Philippine context, the Section 19 of the Article XIV of the 1987 Philippine Constitution stipulated that the state shall promote physical education and encourage sports programs, league competitions, and amateur sports, including training for international competitions, to foster self-discipline, teamwork, and excellence for the development of a healthy and alert citizenry. Furthermore, it also reiterated the need for educational institutions to undertake regular sports activities throughout the country in cooperation with athletic organization and various sectors.

The Department of Education (DepEd) strictly adheres to Executive Order No. 64 , series 1993 or the "Sports for All" policy which addressed the relevance of the sports in rediscovering the traditional and universal values inherent in the practice of sports, such as patriotism, nationalism, self-

discipline, team work and hard work, camaraderie, sportsmanship and fair play, respect for law and order and the rights of others, preservation of our human and natural resources, and the continuing quest for excellence.

To shed light to legal bases of the sports and physical education in the Philippine Educational System, schools need to conceptualize, planned, and organized sports program, training and mentoring sessions, and support mechanisms to Filipino student athletes. As defined by Jacobs (2021), student- athletes are full-time or part-time students of an educational institution who participates in an organized and competitive athletic program offered by the school. Additionally, they are given opportunities to compete, form lasting relationships, develop their leadership and time management skills, and strengthen their work ethics (Durrani, 2020). Moreover, student-athletes must fulfill the responsibilities of both a student and a young athlete. In other words, they must be enrolled in and attend courses offered by the college while also participating in a competitive intercollegiate sport.

In line with the goals of sports as an influential tool to promote human development, stakeholders, organizations, and Philippine educational institutions recognize the need for a sporting culture that nurtures healthy, disciplined, and peaceful citizens and develops Filipino athletes to be at par with the world’s best. Beyond gold and glory, the commitment towards the pursuit of healthy living, community development, self-discipline, and national unity remains.

➤ *Objectives of the Study*

The main objective of the study was to determine the relationship between the extent of schools’ support in sports

training and the performance of student-athletes in sports competition as an input for a Sports Training Plan for the Cluster I Secondary School in the Division of San Pablo City.

Specifically, it sought to determine how the respondents perceived the schools’ support in terms of Academic Support, Sports Equipment and Facilities, Financial Incentives, Health and Well-being, and Capacitating trainers/coaches. Also, it identified the level of student-athletes performance in the Cluster Meet, Division Meet, Regional Meet, and National Meet. Moreover, it determined whether the relationship between the school support and performance of student athletes Is significant or not.

II. METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research design, participants of the study, instrument, data-gathering procedure and data analysis.

➤ *Research Design*

The descriptive correlational design was used in the study. It was used to describe the extent of the schools’ support on sports training, the performance of the student-athletes in sports competitions, and their relationship.

➤ *Respondents of the Study*

The respondents of the study were 166 student-athletes of the schools under the Secondary Cluster I District who have participated in any sports event during the school year 2018-2019, chosen through stratified random sampling. The distribution of the respondents was as follows:

Table 1 Distribution of the Respondents by School

School	No. of Athletes	%	No. of Sample
San Pablo City HIS	134	46.21	77
SPC Science IHS	12	4.14	7
Sto. Anghel NHS	25	8.62	14
San Bartolome NHS	16	5.52	9
Prudencia Fule MNHS	44	15.17	25
Del Remedio NHS	30	10.34	17
Sta. Felomina HIS	12	4.14	7
Dolores NHS	17	5.86	10

➤ *Research Instrument*

The main instrument of the study was a researcher-made questionnaire that would measure the extent of the schools’ support in sports training which was validated by the Master Teachers, Teacher III, and Coaches/Trainer and was tested for its reliability using the Cronbach’s Alpha.

In addition, the independent variables were measured using the likert scale below:

Table 2 The Independent Variables were Measured using the Likert Scale

Score	Scale	VI
4	3.36 – 4.00	To Full Extent
3	2.51 – 3.25	To Moderate Extent
2	1.76 – 2.50	To Some Extent
1	1.00 – 1.75	Not at all

➤ *Research Procedure*

Upon the securing permission from the dean to proceed on the conduct of the study, the researcher forwarded a letter of permit to conduct the study to the Schools Division Superintendent through the Secondary Cluster I Public Schools District Supervisor. Upon the approval, the letter was endorsed to the school heads under the Cluster I schools. The questionnaire was then administered to the respondents.

➤ *Statistical Treatment*

For the descriptive questions, frequency count, percentage, mean scores, and standard deviation were used. To determine if there is a significant relationship between the perceived extent of school’s support on sports training and the performance of the student athletes in different sports competition level, Pearson Product Moment Correlation was employed at 0.05 level of significance.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3 displays the summary table of the student athletes’ assessment on the extent of schools’ support on sports training. Data revealed that generally, the cluster I schools support sports training “To Moderate Extent” (3.31, 0.50). Moreover, it shows that they evaluated the support of the school in terms of Capacitating Trainers/Coaches to be the highest (3.39, 0.51) while the Academic Support to be the lowest (3.23, 0.53).

Analysis shows that although the school provides support of the same level to each of the indicators, they still prioritize the support given to the upskilling of trainers/coaches as they are the primary driver of an athletes’ skill.

Table 3 Summary Table on the Assessment of the Extent of School’s Support on Sports Training

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
Academic Support	3.23	0.53	To Moderate Extent
Sports Equipment and Facilities	3.35	0.48	To Moderate Extent
Financial Incentives	3.34	0.50	To Moderate Extent
Health and Well-being	3.34	0.50	To Moderate Extent
Capacitating Trainers/Coaches	3.39	0.51	To Moderate Extent
Mean	3.31	0.50	To Moderate Extent

The table below shows the summary of the medal tally of the student athletes across all sports level during the S.Y. 2018-2019. The number of medals obtained was multiplied by the weighted score point system 5 points for Gold medals, 3 points for Silver, 2 points for Bronze medal, and 1 point for participation. It can be gleaned that collectively, the athletes scored the highest in the Division Level with a total of 96 medal points, followed by the Cluster Meet Level with 86 points, Regional Level with 30 points, and the lowest in the National Level with zero points.

Additionally, the same was observed in their total weighted points system scores: 32 points for Division Level, 29 points for Cluster Meet Level, 10 points for Regional Level, and no point was recorded for the National Level.

This reveals that the performance of student-athletes at different levels of competition in sports demonstrates how their performance declines as the level of competition rises. Since all athletes competing in such events are already winners, succeeding at a higher level of competition gets harder, but this occurrence is natural.

Table 4 Summary Table on the Assessment of the Extent of School’s Support on Sports Training

Category	Gold	Silver	Bronze	Weighted Point System	VI
Cluster/Unit Meet	65	51	76	29	Fair
Division Level	40	42	36	32	Fair
Regional Level	15	15	20	10	Poor
National Level	-	-	-	-	Poor

*Scale: Outstanding = 81 and above; Very Good = 61-80 pts; Good = 41-60 pts; Fair = 21-40 pts; Poor = 0-20 pts
Medal Point System: Gold = 5 pts; Silver = 3 pts; Bronze = 2 pts*

Table 5 Correlation between the Schools' Support on Sports Training and the Performance of Student Athletes

Schools' Support On Sports Training	Performance of Student Athletes			
	Cluster	Division	Regional	National
Academic Support	-.025	.041	.097	-.066
Sports Equipment and Facilities	-.105	-.103	-.075	-.095
Financial Incentives	-.089	-.074	-.064	-.040
Health and Well-being	-.090	-.087	-.084	-.050
Capacitating Trainers/Coaches	-.103	-.094	-.057	.015

Based on the results, among the indicators of schools' support only the academic support ($r = 0.041$) and capacitating trainers/coaches ($r = 0.015$) exhibited a positive correlation with the students' performance in the Division Level and National Level, respectively. Contrarywise, all other indicators established a negative correlation with the student-athletes' performance in sports competition. Additionally, results show that the perceived extent of schools' support in sports training does not significantly correlate with the student athletes' performance in sports competition at 0.05 level of confidence.

Analysis implied that respondents tended to perceive sufficient provisions of support from the schools, but they were still not able to deliver desirable results. This most likely suggests that the schools' assistance for the athletes and the trainers do not directly affect the performance of student athletes when it comes to winning medals in sports competitions. Thus, the success of student athletes can be attributed to some other factors such as motivational, coaching style, training duration, and many other factors.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

➤ *Conclusions*

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

- There is a significant relationship between the teachers' level of competency in research and the perceived level of the teachers' readiness to conduct research; and the effect of school factors.
- There is a significant relationship between the extent of school factors affecting participation in the conduct of research and challenges in conducting research; level of research productivity; and level of research skills.
- The level of supportive environment significantly mediate the relationship between the teachers' level of research readiness and level of teachers' research skills but does not significantly mediate the teachers' level of research readiness and level of their research productivity.

➤ *Recommendations*

Based on the findings and conclusions, the researcher formulates the following recommendations:

- School heads and or administrators are encouraged to continue the level of support given to the student athletes and their coaches.
- The sports training coordinators, coaches, and trainers were also recommended to develop a sports training plan considering the results of this study.
- Other researchers may explore the relationship between motivational factors, coaching styles, and training duration as determinants of student-athletes' performance in sports competitions.
- Future researches on the effectiveness of the sports training plan developed is highly encouraged.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Baker, J., Cobley, S., & Fraser-Thomas, J. (2009). What do we really know about early sport specialization? Not much! *High Ability Studies*, 20(1), 77-89.
- [2]. Bay N. (2008). Evaluation of Safety of Sport Facilities in Golestan Master's thesis. Faculty of Physical Education and Sports Science, Tehran University
- [3]. Burke, S. M., Shapcott, K. M., Carron, A. V., Bradshaw, M. H., & Estabrooks, P. A. (2010). Group goal setting and group performance in a physical activity context. *International Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 8, 245-261.
- [4]. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2006). Sports-related injuries among high school athletes: United States, 2005-06 school year. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report*, 55(38), 1037-1040.
- [5]. Davids, K. (2015). Athletes and sports teams as complex adaptive system: a review of implications for learning design. *Rev. Int. Cienc. Deporte* 39, 48-61. doi: 10.5232/ricyde2015.03904
- [6]. Goldstein, E. R., Ziegenfuss, T., Kalman, D., Kreider, R., Campbell, B., Wilborn, C., et al. (2010). International society of sports nutrition position stand: caffeine and performance. *Journal of the International Society of Sports Nutrition*, 7(1), 5. doi:10.1186/1550-2783-7-5
- [7]. Jeme, E. O. (2007). Enforcing the three dimensions of school sports. *The Nation Newspaper* 30/8/2009 Lagos: Vintage Press Ltd.
- [8]. Kreider, R. B., Wilborn, C. D., Taylor, L., Campbell, B., Almada, A. L., Collins, R., et al. (2010). ISSN exercise & sport nutrition review: research & recommendations. *Journal of the International Society of Sports Nutrition*, 7, 7. doi:10.1186/1550-2783-7-7
- [9]. Lawrence, M. (1999). Sport science summit report. Colorado Springs, Colorado: USA Swimming.
- [10]. Miquelon, P., & Vallerand, R. J. (2017). Goal motives, well-being, and physical health: An integrative model. *Canadian Psychology*, 49, 241-249.
- [11]. Montinari, & Piovesan. (2016). Do not trash the incentive! Monetary incentives and waste sorting. In Harvard Business School working paper (pp. 11-93).
- [12]. Moosa, I. A., & Smith, L. (2014). Economic development indicators as determinants of medal winning at the Sydney Olympics: An extreme bounds analysis. *Australian Economic Papers*, 43, 288-301
- [13]. Palomino, F. A., & Rigotti, L. (2015). The sport league's dilemma: Competitive balance versus incentives to win (Discussion Paper 2000-109). Center for Economic Research, Tilburg University
- [14]. Mensch, J. Crews, C., & Mitchell, M. (2005). Competing perspectives during organizational socialization on the role of certified athletic trainers in high school settings. *Journal of Athletic Training*, 40(4), 333-340.
- [15]. Miller, M.G., & Berry, D. C. (2011). *Emergency Response Management for Athletic Trainers*. Baltimore, MD: Lippincott, Williams & Wilkins.

- [16]. National Council of Youth Sports. (2008). Report on trends and participation in organized youth sports. Retrieved December 8, 2010, from <http://www.ncys.org/publications/2008-sports-participation-study.php>
- [17]. Ogundairo, D. O. (2010). Physical and health education for Colleges of Education. Ibadan: Rex Charles Press.
- [18]. Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2015). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *American Psychologist*, 55, 68-78.
- [19]. Vallerand, R. J., & Rousseau, F. L. (2013). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in sport and exercise: A review using the hierarchical model of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. In R. N.
- [20]. Singer, H. A. Hausenblas, & C. M. Janelle (Eds.), *Handbook of sport psychology* (2nd ed., pp. 389-416). New York: Wiley.
- [21]. Yang, D., & Leung, A. (2016). The politics of sports anti-doping in China: Crisis, governance and international compliance. *China: An International Journal*, 6, 121-148.
- [22]. Yavuz, N. (2014). The use of non-monetary incentives as a motivational tool: A survey study in a public organisation in Turkey. Middle East Technical University.